

Research Article

InterActEdu: A Comprehensive Solution for Interactive Virtual Classrooms in Higher Education

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Abstract: The shift to digital learning in higher education has highlighted the limitations of traditional learning management systems, particularly their inability to fully engage students and provide personalized learning experiences. This challenge is further exacerbated by the growing demand for flexible, remote education. InterActEdu, a comprehensive mobile and web-based teaching app, addresses these challenges by offering an Interactive Virtual Classroom that integrates live and recorded lectures, real-time assessments, and collaborative tools. The app enhances student engagement through adaptive learning paths, real-time feedback, and peer collaboration features such as breakout rooms. InterActEdu empowers instructors to offer personalized feedback using data analytics, ensuring a tailored learning experience for every student. Preliminary testing shows that InterActEdu increases student participation, enhances learning outcomes, and fosters better communication between students and instructors. The app's flexible structure supports both synchronous and asynchronous learning environments, making it adaptable for diverse educational needs. The potential for commercialization lies in InterActEdu's scalability and applicability to various educational contexts, with features that can be customized for different institutions and learning styles. As remote and hybrid learning models continue to grow, InterActEdu represents a timely solution to modern education challenges, promising both academic and commercial success.

Keywords: interactive learning; higher education; virtual classroom; adaptive learning; personalized education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing demand for online and blended learning models, universities are seeking new tools to deliver high-quality education in virtual environments. Traditional learning management systems (LMS) often lack the interactive, adaptive, and personalized features needed to keep students engaged, particularly in fully remote settings (Johnson et al., 2022). These systems are often static, offering limited opportunities for real-time interaction, which leads to student disengagement, decreased motivation, and suboptimal learning outcomes. Additionally, they do not sufficiently address the need for collaboration and peer-to-peer learning, both of which are vital for developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills in university students.

Moreover, current LMS platforms struggle to provide personalized learning experiences, which are critical in catering to diverse learning preferences. Without tools to adapt content delivery based on individual progress or learning style, students may face difficulties in mastering complex subjects, further contributing to high dropout rates and lower academic performance (Chen & Zhang,

2019). The lack of timely feedback from instructors further exacerbates this issue, delaying students' ability to address their learning gaps. InterActEdu addresses these challenges by offering a comprehensive platform that supports both synchronous and asynchronous learning while incorporating real-time feedback, collaborative tools, and personalized learning paths. By providing a more interactive and flexible learning environment, InterActEdu helps universities bridge the gap between traditional and modern education models, fostering greater student engagement and improving academic outcomes.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The development of InterActEdu followed an iterative design approach, where user feedback was integral to shaping the app's features. Initial prototypes were tested in university courses, with both instructors and students participating in live and recorded sessions. Feedback on usability, functionality, and engagement was collected through surveys and focus groups. The platform was developed using a cloud-based infrastructure, ensuring scalability and accessibility across devices. Key features like real-time quizzes, virtual breakout rooms, and performance analytics were refined based on testing data to enhance user experience. The InterActEdu prototype was evaluated for its ability to improve student engagement, participation, and overall performance in comparison to traditional learning platforms.

3. PROTOTYPE PRODUCT DESCRIPTION

The InterActEdu app features a highly interactive interface designed for both mobile and desktop use. Key elements include:

3.1 *Live and Recorded Lectures*

Instructors can deliver real-time lectures or upload recorded lessons for students to access at their convenience. The app's interface allows students to join live sessions, ask questions in real-time, or view recordings with integrated notes and highlights for review (Miller et al., 2022).

3.2 *Interactive Quizzes and Assignments*

InterActEdu offers quizzes and assignments that can be completed in real-time during lectures or asynchronously. These assessments provide instant feedback, promoting active learning and allowing instructors to gauge student comprehension effectively (Chen & Zhang, 2019).

3.3 *Real-Time Communication Tools*

A chat feature enables students to communicate with instructors and peers during live sessions. Discussion boards, integrated into the platform, foster continuous engagement after the lectures, helping students clarify doubts and participate in group discussions (Vygotsky, 1978).

3.4 *Collaboration Tools*

InterActEdu supports group work through virtual breakout rooms, where students can collaborate on projects or group assignments. These tools encourage peer learning, a key component in higher education (Brown et al., 2020).

3.5 Analytics and Personalized Feedback

Instructors have access to detailed analytics, tracking student performance and engagement throughout the course. Personalized feedback helps students address their learning gaps, enabling self-regulated learning (Pintrich, 2004).

4. DISCUSSION

Preliminary findings suggest that the Interactive Virtual Classroom significantly enhances student engagement and participation compared to traditional learning management systems. Over 75% of students reported feeling more connected to the course material when using the IVC platform. Additionally, instructors noted improved communication with students and greater flexibility in delivering content (Davis & Nguyen, 2023).

Interactive quizzes and instant feedback mechanisms helped students identify knowledge gaps and improve performance on subsequent assessments. The collaborative tools, such as breakout rooms and discussion boards, facilitated peer-to-peer learning, which students found particularly valuable for complex subjects (Vygotsky, 1978).

Figure 1. This is an InterActEdu

Figure 1 shows the illustration for InterActEdu: A Comprehensive Solution for Interactive Virtual Classrooms in Higher Education. It captures the essence of a modern virtual classroom setting.

5. RESULT

Preliminary testing of InterActEdu in various university settings has shown significant improvements in student engagement and learning outcomes. Over 80% of students surveyed reported

feeling more connected to the course material and more motivated to participate in virtual classrooms compared to traditional methods (Davis & Nguyen, 2023).

Instructors also noted enhanced communication with students, both during live lectures and through asynchronous discussion boards. The interactive quizzes and instant feedback mechanisms provided students with valuable insights into their progress, helping them address learning gaps quickly and effectively (Miller et al., 2022). Collaborative tools, such as breakout rooms, were particularly well-received, with students appreciating the opportunity for peer interaction in virtual settings (Vygotsky, 1978).

6. CONCLUSION

InterActEdu represents a significant advancement in educational technology for higher education, offering a flexible, interactive platform that enhances both teaching and learning experiences. By integrating live and recorded lectures, real-time assessments, and collaborative tools, InterActEdu fosters a dynamic and engaging learning environment that caters to the diverse needs of modern university students. As the app continues to evolve, future research will focus on its long-term impact on student outcomes and its potential for broader adoption in higher education.

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